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ASPECTS OF THE IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL TOURIST FLOW ON EMPLOYMENT

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Abstract

The article examines the influence of seasonality of international tourist flows on their distribution by regions of the world and the definition of aspects of the impact of tourism and travel on the level of employment in the country based on a comparative analysis of different countries. The direct and indirect contributions of tourism to the economy are revealed, the main tourist markets that form international tourist flows are highlighted. The sphere of tourism and travel is of great importance in providing employment for the population. This makes it possible to identify favorable tourist resources and new products for the development of tourism in various regions of the world, as well as to develop a tourism development strategy at the level of international standards.

The significance of the study lies in the fact that the data and results obtained make it possible to realize the significance of the issue under study and the need to study it.

Keywords: *international tourism, regions, distribution, population, employment, provision*

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism today has become a rapidly developing industry in many countries, being an industry of the socio-economic complex. Currently, every 7th workplace in the world is accounted for by organizations engaged in the tourism business. According to WTO forecasts, by 2025 the number of international tourist trips will amount to about 1.7 billion people. Estimates show that the daily expenses of tourists, with the exception of air transportation, will increase to \$5 billion per day [21].

Currently, there are two trends in tourism:

- impact of external economic and political factors;
- the ability of tourism volumes to recover quickly under unfavorable conditions [Kazybaykyzy, 2015: 265-269].

Stability in the global financial markets has led to some changes in the habits of vacationing tourists: the number of bookings for this period and beyond has increased, and tourist spending on holidays has decreased. From the above, it can be concluded that tourism became a deeply rooted part of culture at the end of the twentieth century.

Tourism in Azerbaijan is a developing complex. Therefore, the market is constantly looking for new forms of work, ways to solve problems arising in this industry. Despite the rapid pace of development of the tourism sector in recent years, with the exception of the pandemic period, currently the share of this sector in the country's GDP (5.5-6.9%) in those years did not have very high quantitative indicators [26].

The economy of the country as a whole is associated with obtaining the optimal effect through the use of limited resources. As a rule, limited economic factors or resources, including tourism, are designed to meet the psychological and physical needs of a person.

The main purpose of the article is to study the influence of seasonality of international tourist flows on

their distribution by regions of the world and to find out the impact of tourism and travel on the level of employment in the country based on a comparative analysis of different countries.

The theoretical and practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the data and results obtained as a result of the study make it possible to realize the significance of the issue under study and the need to study it.

Seasonality is an interdisciplinary concept that includes a change in the number of people visiting a certain tourist place. Seasonality also affects the marketing policy of the tourist market, the labor market and financial flows. Today, the influence of seasonality on all spheres of the economy is undeniable. Thus, tourism is a commercial destination, and any business is subject to seasonal changes. One of the important factors that needs to be studied in order to get the most out of the tourist market is seasonality [Konstantinova, 2019: 1-8]. The dictionary of business terms contains information about the change of the season of the year, about the period of performance of certain works, as well as about traditions, holidays, etc. the economic processes associated with it are considered seasonal.

In some studies, tourism is defined as the seasonality of tourist activity, recurring from year to year, which is characteristic of the place (territory) under study and is associated with changes in recreational conditions [Sharafanova, 2015: 30-40].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

From the point of view of the activity and development of the tourism sector in Azerbaijan, there are comprehensive opportunities. In this regard, unlike a number of countries where the tourism sector is developed, in order to support the development of this sphere at the required level, the state conducts a special policy, which also reflects the strategy of tourism development and its phased solution [18]. Compared with foreign countries, Azerbaijan has truly unique natural, cultural,

and architectural monuments, including about 38 architectural monuments of world significance: Ateshgah, Icheri Sheher, Muhammad Mosque, Maiden Tower, Shirvanshah Palace, Seyid Yahya and Shirvanshah mausoleums, etc. are available [23]. It should also be noted that Azerbaijan receives only 0.02-0.03% of the international tourist flow around the world, while our country, according to approximate estimates, has the ability to receive up to 10 million tourists a year. It should be noted that the development of tourism in Azerbaijan was also negatively affected by the state of emergency that occurred in the world (the COVID-19 pandemic), which is 3.15 times higher than the number of tourists received in the year preceding the pandemic (2019) [19, pp. 21-25].

Tourism experienced the most serious crisis in the history of observations in 2020 after an unprecedented emergency in the field of health, social and economic situation amid the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. This crisis led to a reduction in the number of international tourists (overnight guests) in 2020 by 74% compared to the previous 2019, which had a negative impact on the travel of international tourists, and the tourism industry worldwide faced a loss of export revenues worth 1.3 trillion US dollars. It should be noted that during this emergency, the tourism sector suffered 11 times more total losses than during the global economic crisis of 2009.

According to the annual report of the World Economic Forum in the field of tourism and travel for 2021, Azerbaijan ranked (72nd) among 194 countries of the world in terms of attractiveness for foreign tourists, being above the average by 20 countries. The tourist flow is understood as the movement of tourists from a certain place, place of residence (supplier market) to other places (the core of attraction) that have some resources and tourist offer (receiving the market). The change of

tourist destinations and its conjunctural changes may be due to motivational (fatigue from overloaded and noisy centers), economic (inflation, exchange rate), social and other reasons.

The main tourist markets generating the flow of tourists at the international level are:

- In Europe: markets of Central Europe and Northern Europe (Germany, Benelux countries, Great Britain, France, Scandinavian Peninsula countries);
- In America: Canada and the USA;
- In Asia: Japan.

The main international markets that receive tourists include:

- In Europe: countries of the Mediterranean countries of Europe, Asia and Africa; especially between the countries of the European Union, intra-European exchange plays an important role;
- In Asia: Middle East (Israel, Egypt, Turkey, Jordan, Syria); Hindustan Peninsula: India, Nepal; South-east Asian countries: Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, etc.;
- In America: USA, Mexico, Caribbean countries, Peru and Brazil;
- In Africa: Maghreb countries, Egypt, Kenya, Indian Ocean islands (Seychelles, Maldives and Mauritius).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. CONTRIBUTION OF TOURISM TO THE ECONOMY

In order to identify the structural features of tourism organizations based on the methodology of the World Tourism Organization, the World Council for Tourism and Travel, the contribution of the tourism sector to the economy is systematized according to the characteristics: direct, indirect and individual impact (Table 1).

Table 1

Characteristics of the impact of the contribution of tourism to the country's economy		
Brief description of the contribution of tourism to the economy		
Straight	Indirect	Individual
<p>Hotel tourism services: accommodation, meals, transport, religious-cultural-historical-ecological attractions, entertainment.</p> <p>Areas of direct impact: mass accommodation facilities (hotel, otel, motel, etc.), transport, travel agencies, tour operators, retail, culture, sports, recreation.</p> <p>Sources of income to the country's budget from tourism: residents' expenses on tourism and travel, non-residents' expenses (export of tourist services), residents' expenses on business trips, individual government expenses</p>	<p>Investments aimed at the tourism sector</p> <p>Government spending on tourism in general</p> <p>Domestic supplies and purchases</p>	<p>Material and technical support of specialized tourism enterprises</p> <p>Goods and services that ensure the livelihoods of workers in this field: food, beverages, clothing, housing services and agriculture</p>

Note: based on [Kapustin, 2014: 35-43] compiled by the author

The direct contribution of tourism to the economy is recorded directly in the service sector, which is related to the quantitative and qualitative indicators of the services provided to tourists. The indirect impact of tourism on the country's economy directly covers a wide range of types of tourism and related enterprises that support the activities of specialized tourism enterprises and their service personnel. It should be noted that the tourism industry directly contributes to the formation of added value in the country's GDP and in the service sector. And taking into account additional enterprises and related enterprises, this increases the indirect and induction incomes of the entire complex of the "tourist economy".

For a broader explanation of the contribution of the tourism sector to the country's economy, consider its share in world GDP (Fig.1).

Figure 1. The share of tourism and travel in GDP

Source: based on [26] compiled by the author

A number of studies have concluded that tourism and the hotel business create various business opportunities in such sectors as housing, catering and beverage companies, transport services, travel agencies, travel companies, natural and cultural tourism [Syntaexn et al.: 2016, 7-9].

So, in the sphere of accommodation (accommodation) and catering (catering) of tourists, respectively, giant chains of hotels and restaurants have been formed. For example, the number of real estate objects included in the largest hotels and resorts in the world is shown in Table 2.

The analysis shows that the top five leading hotel companies in the world include Wyndham Hotels &

Resorts (8941 properties), International Marriott (7662 properties), World Hotels (7111 properties), Hilton (6619 properties) and ICN Hotels & Resorts (5959 properties). Among these 15 leading hotel companies, Westmont Hospitality Group, which is in the last five (11th - 15th places), has -736 properties, Red Roff -668 properties, Extended Stey Mnenka -653 properties, Highdate -366 properties and Apple Hospitality RPT -232 properties. It should also be noted that the number of Apple Hospitality RPT properties, which are in last place among the leading hotel companies, is 38.5 times, or 8,709 units less than that of Wyndham Hotels and Resorts.

Table 2

The number of real estate properties of the world's leading hotel companies as of September 2021, units.

n/a	The world's largest hotel and restaurant chains with accommodation facilities and catering facilities	The number of real estate objects in the largest hotels and resorts
1	Wyndham Hotels and Resorts	8941
2	International Marriott	7662
3	Hotels of the World	7111
4	Hilton	6619
5	ICH hotels and Resorts	5959
6	The best hotels and resorts on the West Coast	4039
7	Radisson Group Hotel	1615
8	C6 Hospitality	1393
9	Cambridge Hospital	1380
10	Hyatt Hotels Corporation	1020
11	Westmont Hospitality Group	736
12	Red Roff	668
13	Mnenca Extended Steak	653
14	Hidhdates	366
15	Apple Hospital RPT	232

Source: based on data [21] compiled by the author

3.2. TOURISM COMPETITIVENESS INDEX AND INTERNATIONAL TOURIST RECEPTION IN THE REGIONS

The World Economic Forum annually determines the ranking of the countries of the world (by 195 countries) according to the travel and tourism competitiveness index. When determining the ranking of countries, a set of data from common sources, information from international information organizations, experts in the field of travel and tourism is used. These data provide favorable conditions for making the right decisions by States seeking to improve the travel and tourism sector. In the process of analysis, the article used methods of comparison (benchmarking) and interstate regression analysis with the most advanced countries.

The results of the analysis show that Spain, France, Germany, Japan, BB, USA, Australia, Switzerland, Italy and Canada (within 5.43-4.97 points) entered the top ten leading countries in terms of the average index of competition in the tourism sector [28]. In the last ten countries are Burundi, Chad, Yemen, Mauritania, Congo, Sierra Leone, Mali, Nigeria, Lesotho and Cameroon (border 2.88-2.44 points). Among the countries of the former Soviet Union, Estonia, Russia, Latvia, Lithuania, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Armenia, Ukraine, Kyrgyzstan are in the top ten (the limit is 4.23-5.31 points). According to the travel and tourism competitiveness index, Azerbaijan ranked 73rd among 195 countries.

It should be noted that according to the assessment based on 14 components reflecting the competitiveness of tourism by country, it is possible to compile an exhaustive map of the best tourism destinations in the world. One of the evaluation indicators is the development of tourism infrastructure in the country, which determines how well the country copes with the reception

and accommodation of tourists, takes into account the number of hotel beds per 1000 people, the number of tourist infrastructure, as well as the number of ATMs for every 1000 elderly people [Roudy and etc, 2019:1280-1300].

A comparative analysis of the international reception of tourists in the regions of the world in 2018-2020 shows that compared to 2018 in the European region in 2019, this figure increased by 30.3 million, or 4.2%, and in 2020-by 480.9 million, or 67.2%. This figure increased by 13.9 million or 4% in the Asia-Pacific region in 2019 and decreased by 289.4 million or 83.5% in 2020, respectively. In addition, the reception of international tourists in the American region increased by 3.3 million in 2019 and by 146.3 million in 2020. In the African region, this figure increased by 1.4 million in 2019 and decreased by 50.5 million in 2020. At the same time, this figure in the Middle East region increased by 5 million in 2019, and decreased by 47.3 million in 2020. According to this indicator, an increase of 0.053 million was observed worldwide in 2019, and a decrease of 47.3 million in 2020.

In 2020, the number of international trips in the Asia-Pacific region decreased by 83.5%, which is almost 303.3 million less than last year. The number of arrivals in the Middle East and Africa decreased by 51.8 million, or 74%. The number of arrivals to Europe decreased and amounted to 235.1 million. This is 67.2% less than the number of international tourists in 2018. In general, in North and South America, the decrease in the number of foreign tourists in 2018 compared to 2020 was 67.7%. Compared to 2018, the number of international tourists worldwide in 2020 decreased by 1015 million, or 71.8% (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Arrival of international tourists in the regions of the world

Source: based on data [21] compiled by the author

When mitigating the problem of unemployment (the influx of citizens abroad reduces the intensity of unemployment in the country, reduces the supply of labor), along with the positive consequences, it is necessary to take into account the negative consequences that may arise due to the influx of tourists from certain regions. So, if there is not enough labor in the region, then this may affect the emergence of certain stagnations in the tourism industry, as well as in agriculture. The migration of the population from rural to urban areas will increase the burden on non-productive areas such as health and education. Also, the investment resources spent on additional investments in the tourism sector will not be able to be directed to those areas that they need.

For example, the advantage of our tourists traveling abroad compared to the entry of foreign tourists to Azerbaijan leads to the actual transfer of the country's currency funds to the economy of other countries. Statistics show that the number of local tourists traveling abroad is very large, and the ratio of these two indicators in Azerbaijan is within 1:2.04 in 2015 and 1:1.46 in 2020 [19, p.20]. It should also be noted that the tourism sector is considered vulnerable in the development of the economy of this country, when the number of tourists leaving and coming to the leading developed countries is 1:5.

The main factor hindering the faster development of outbound tourism in Azerbaijan is the low purchasing power of monetary incomes of the majority of the population. Because the crisis of recent years in the world, the military conflict between Russia and Ukraine and the latest waves of the pandemic have inevitably affected the purchasing power of monetary incomes of the population. For example, in 2021, the average monthly salary of the population amounted to \$ 416.3 (707.7 manats), and its purchasing power for goods decreased by 35-45% compared to 2019. In our opinion, if in the coming years it is possible to reverse

this negative trend and stimulate income growth, this process will have a positive impact on the organization of tourist trips of the local population in our country and will contribute to the rapid development of tourism.

Thus, the most important organizational and economic problems of the entry of foreign tourists to Azerbaijan can be attributed to two main issues. On the one hand, with an increase in the standard of living and well-being of the population living in Azerbaijan, the volume of mobile tourism will increase, which will undoubtedly increase the demand for services by the consumer of the country. At the same time, it is necessary to regulate both the standard of service and the level of prices for tourist services. On the other hand, inbound tourism to the country is an important source of foreign exchange earnings. The decrease in the volume of inbound tourism requires domestic firms hosting tourists to analyze the reasons for the lack of interest in our country among tourists from abroad. In this regard, tourism, in our opinion, has an impact on the country's economy in almost all aspects of the fundamental definition of this sphere of society.

3.3. ASPECTS OF THE IMPACT OF TOURISM ON EMPLOYMENT

International tourism has become an important source of foreign exchange earnings for many developed and developing countries [Ismayilov, 2017: 562-569]. The growing importance of tourism in the economic development of an increasing number of countries confirms the assumption that international tourism revenues will gradually increase. According to the World Tourism and Travel Council, in 2021, the share of people employed in world tourism accounts for 9.9% of those employed in all sectors of the economy. Forecasts show that in 2022 the number of people employed in tourism will amount to 10.2% of the world's employed population.

An analysis of the number of people employed in the areas characteristic of tourism in the countries of the

world and Azerbaijan, which entered the top ten in 2018-2019, shows that only in Angola there is an increase in the number of people employed in this direction by 363 thousand people. But despite this growth, the rating of this country in 2018 decreased by one notch compared to the previous year and took 11th place. It should be noted that among the compared countries, the smallest decrease in the number of people employed in tourism-specific areas occurred in Belarus (1,000 people), Chile (4,000 people) and Azerbaijan (6,000 people).

The largest decrease in this indicator occurred in the Philippines, which are in the second place of the rating -349 thousand people, in Spain-69 thousand people, Greece-27 thousand people, Turkey-21 thousand

people, Morocco-17 thousand people and Algeria-12 thousand people. Also among the compared countries, the percentage of decrease in the number of admissions compared to 2018 was in Greece-7.8%; in the Philippines-6.1%; in Algeria-3.8%; in Morocco-3% and Spain-2.6%. Among the compared countries, the lowest percentage of decline was in Belarus-0%; Chile-0.9% and Turkey-1.9%. The largest was in Azerbaijan, which dropped from 26th to 46th place in 2018, and dropped from 20th to 20th place in 2019. At that time, the drop in the rating in Belarus was 14 row.

In our opinion, the decrease in the number of people employed in tourism-specific areas in 2019 compared to 2018 can be illustrated by the pandemic situation that has already begun in these countries (Table 3).

Table 3

The number of people employed in industries specific to tourism, thousand people

Countries	Years			Increase (+) or decrease (-) in 2019 compared to 2018
	2018	Country rating	Country rating	
Philippines	5714	1	5365	-6,1%
Spain	2674	2	2605	-2,6%
Turkey	1600	3	1569	-1,9%
Morocco	565	4	548	-3,0%
Chile	442	5	438	-0,9%
Indonesia	409	6	400	-2,2%
Greece	347	7	320	-7,8%
Algeria	320	8	308	-3,8%
Belarusian	243	9	242	-0,4%
Angola	216	10	579	+1,68 times
...	...		...	...
Azerbaijan	59	20	53	-10,1%

Source: based on [Employment in Tourism Industries: 2018-2019] compiled by the author

Based on a comparative analysis of the number of people employed in the spheres characteristic of tourism in Azerbaijan, it can be noted that in 2016, compared with 2015, there was a decrease of 12.1%; in 2017 - by 5.3% and in 2020 - by 0.9%, only in 2018 - by 7.6% and in 2019 year-by 19.2%. In our opinion, the presence of such an increase in the number of people employed in tourism-specific destinations in 2018-2019 compared to 2015 may be due to an increase in the number of international tourists traveling to the country in those years and an increase in their service personnel.

An analysis of the number of jobs created in tourism and travel around the world in 2019-2021 shows that in subsequent years, due to the consequences of the extraordinary pandemic conditions that began at the end of 2019, the number of jobs in this area decreased

by 62 million or 18.6% in 2020; and by 44 million or 13.2% in 2021 (Figure 1) [29].

The equation of approximation of the trend of job cuts in tourism and travel around the world is written as (1):

$$Y = -45.37 \ln(x) + 324.76 \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) allows us to investigate the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of jobs created in the field of tourism and travel, directs the question under study to the study of simpler or more convenient objects. This equation shows that the theoretical prices for the number of jobs created by tourism and travel around the world are relatively close to experimental prices. This also reflects the adequacy of this model. In addition, the results of the study suggest a long-term asymmetric relationship between the impact of tourism and travel on employment.

Chart 1. Number of jobs in tourism and travel around the world

Source: based on data from [Syntaexn atc, 2016:12] compiled by the author

IV. CONCLUSIONS

International tourism, becoming an important source of foreign exchange earnings for countries, increasingly increases its importance in the economic development of countries and confirms the assumption that revenues from international tourism will increase. The crisis of recent years, as well as the military conflict between Russia and Ukraine and the recent waves of the pandemic have inevitably had a negative impact on the purchasing power of monetary incomes of the population. If in the coming years it is possible to reverse this negative trend and stimulate income growth, then rapid development of tourism will be achieved in the country, which will have a positive impact on the organization of tourist trips of the local population in their territories. In our opinion, the decline in 2019-2021 in the number of people employed in tourism-specific areas compared to 2018 can be illustrated by the pandemic conditions that have already begun in these countries and are currently continuing in various waves.

The sphere of tourism and travel is of great importance in providing employment for the population. This makes it possible to identify favorable tourist resources and new products for the development of tourism in various regions of the world and accurately identify tourist resources, as well as correctly formulate a strategy for their development in this direction.

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